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Stress Tolerance in Traditional Fermented Foods: A Microbial Niche for Resilient Bacteria

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Abstract

Traditionally prepared fermented foods are known to be important sources of beneficial microorganisms having unique ecological niches. Fermentative bacteria such as lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are known to thrive in harsh environments like extreme pH, temperature and salt concentration. The primary objectives of this study were - firstly, to isolate LAB such as *Lactobacillus* sp. from selected fermented foods that are locally made in the northeastern region of India. Secondly, to determine bacterial capability to withstand harsh environmental parameters such as nutrient limitations, pH variations, high salinity and temperature conditions. Preliminary screening and isolation of bacteria were done using MRS (De Man, Rogosa and Sharpe) agar. All isolates selected for this study were all gram-positive bacteria and only one of them exhibited catalase activity. In this study, microbial growth and viability test were performed by estimation of optical density as well as colony-forming units (CFU ml⁻¹), respectively. Based on our results, two isolates, LS and FM were able to form colonies at highly acidic medium of pH 2.5. One of the isolates (BK) was found to exhibit viability in oxygen-limited and nutrient-limited conditions such as glucose, magnesium, as well as sodium acetate. Growth declined significantly in the absence of glucose, however, the presence of alternative carbon sources may significantly contribute to the formation of viable cells. The formation of colonies in a non-aerated (oxygen-limited) culture condition also demonstrated the facultative anaerobic trait of the isolate. The salt tolerance test in isolates LS and DF indicated that bacterial cells could withstand high salinity even at 10 % NaCl. Besides, the capability to form biofilm at different temperatures could also be another advantage for promoting bacterial colonization against competing microorganisms and pathogens.

Keywords: Lactic acid bacteria; Fermented foods; Colony forming units; Lactobacillus; MRS media; Stress

Introduction

The process of fermentation involves conversion of foods by microorganisms, as well as enzymes generated by these microbes. Breakdown of carbohydrates in foods or beverages by microbes such as bacteria and fungi is employed mostly for preservation; however, it is also utilized to improve the organoleptic qualities of food by producing distinct flavors, which might result in new food product variations (Heller, 2001). Fermented foods consist of beneficial bacteria or probiotics such as lactic acid bacteria (Parvez et al., 2006) and the process of fermentation can minimize the levels of toxic and unwanted impurities.

Microbial metabolism leads to breakdown of complex compounds and synthesis of growth factors as well as complex vitamins. Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are fermentative microorganisms that may develop at a variety of pH levels when organic acids are present and are abundant in the guts of healthy animals. Fermentation byproducts mainly acids and alcohols can prevent the growth of common food pathogens such as *Clostridium botulinum* at pH ≤ 4.6 (Hasan et al., 2014). As LAB produces organic acids, the pH drops, and the environment becomes more hostile to microorganisms that are less acid-tolerant (Rault et al., 2009; Mallick and Das, 2023). Therefore,

because maintaining pH homeostasis requires more energy, organic acids in the media could contribute to growth suppression. The organisms now employed in probiotic products, in addition to lactic acid bacteria, include different species of yeasts or *Saccharomyces*, *Bacillus* and fungi such as *Aspergillus* (Papadimitriou et al., 2016). The demand for probiotic products for consumption due to their health benefits has gained popularity worldwide.

In lactic acid bacteria, acid stress is considered to be self-imposed since lactic acid is the main byproduct when sugar is fermented. It is advantageous for the LAB for survival against the other competing bacterial populations which cannot tolerate the acidic environment. However, the lactic acid buildup may have implications even for this acid-tolerant LAB in the long run (Rault et al., 2009; Mallick and Das, 2023). LAB such as *Lactobacillus plantarum* is able to ferment sugar to lactic acid and tolerate acidic pH to survive such acidic conditions were described in (Heunis et al., 2014). *E. coli* can tolerate and survive in a wide range of osmotic environments ranging from 0.036% to 0.18% in the lumen to much higher concentrations in a food system (McClure, 2005). Salt has been an important ingredient in fermentation and dehydration for food preservation since ancient times. Salt can affect microorganisms depending on various inherent and extrinsic variables. The sensitivity of microorganisms to salt may differ intrinsically (Durack, 2008). Salt is a common element in the production of fermented foods such as pickles and sauerkraut. Salt regulates microbial development by allowing beneficial microorganisms to flourish in the vegetable substrate, creating the conditions for healthy fermentation (Gandhi & Shah, 2016; Varzakas et al., 2017).

A deeper knowledge in understanding the mechanisms involved in salt tolerance might lead to more applications in commercial food processing. There has been less extensive investigation of the salt tolerance response in *Lactobacillus* so far. Healthy bacteria found in certain fermented ingredients produce enzymes that break down the food in the intestine which enhance the absorption of nutrients with ease. Similarly, the useful microorganism also produces vitamins along with the water-soluble nutrients B and C, making fermented foods richer in vitamins. Here in this study, we assessed different parameters like growth, viability and biofilm formation to validate the bacterial tolerance towards environmental stress factors including nutrient limitation, low temperature, pH variation, and different salt concentrations.

Material and methods

Sample collection

Fermented food samples produced from fish, milk, soybean and mustard leaves were collected from local markets in northeast region of India such as Mizoram and Manipur. Serially diluted samples were spread on MRS (De Man, et al., 1960) agar and incubated at 37°C for 18 hrs. Bacterial single colonies that appeared on MRS agar plate were selected for obtaining pure cultures and preserved at -80°C as glycerol stocks. A bacterial colony from each fermented food product was selected for morphological and biochemical analysis as shown in Table 1.

Preliminary characterization of isolates

Selected bacteria were characterized by checking attributes such as growth, gram staining properties and catalase activity. For estimation of bacterial growth, cell density was measured by taking absorbance at 600 nm and colony forming units per ml (CFU ml⁻¹) was determined from serially diluted samples on MRS plate incubated at 37°C overnight. Gram staining was performed by standard protocol as described earlier (Bartholomew & Mittwer 1952). Catalase activity was checked by the occurrence of bubbles in the presence of hydrogen peroxide.

Growth estimation under limiting conditions

MRS media were prepared with or without magnesium sulphate, sodium acetate, and glucose. The cultures were distributed equally in glass test tubes sealed with cotton plugs and were incubated at 37°C. OD₆₀₀ was measured at different time points for 0 hr, 18 hr and 36 hr. Simultaneously, another set of experiments with similar conditions was subjected to limited aeration by using air-tight or sealed culture flasks.

Salt tolerance assay

Bacterial tolerance to salt stress was conducted on the isolates with different NaCl concentrations of 0.5%, 1.0%, 1.5%, 2.0%, 4.5%, 8.5%, 10.5% and 11.5% using MRS broth. The broth was distributed in small conical flask and appropriate concentrations of NaCl were added respectively. 5 ml of each was pipetted out into different test tubes and 100µl each of bacterial samples were

added into each test tube. The test tubes were then left for incubation. Bacterial growth was checked at different time points by measuring optical density at 600 nm.

Acid tolerance assay

Bacterial cultures were sub-cultured at least 2 times followed by inoculation in MRS media with varying pH (6.5, 5.5, 4.5, 3.5, 2.5, and 1.5). The pH of the media was adjusted by adding hydrochloric acid. Growth was measured at time interval of 0, 20, and 34 hours by using spectrophotometer. By comparing the colony forming unit (CFU ml⁻¹) on the plates with the absorbance readings, the acid tolerance was estimated.

Biofilm assay

Bacterial cultures were allowed to grow on agar plates as well as in liquid media and incubated at different temperature (37°C and 6-7°C). For liquid medium, bacterial growth was checked at different time points by spectrophotometric method at 600 nm as done earlier. An equal amount of bacterial culture was inoculated in 96-well flat bottom plates. Biofilms were fixed with methanol (99%) after removing planktonic cells, and plates were air-dried after washing properly with sterile water or PBS. Then, 0.2% crystal violet solution was added to the wells and washed after 5 minutes incubation. Finally, 33% acetic acid was added and absorbance was measured at 575 nm using a microplate reader to estimate biofilm growth (Shukla et al., 2020).

Statistical analysis

In all tests, bacterial growth was taken as the quantitative variable by recording spectrophotometric measurement at OD₆₀₀ as well as estimation of CFU per ml. All studies were conducted in replicates to ensure the reliability and accuracy of the data collected.. Each data point is the average or mean of different experimental replicates with a maximum deviation <10%. Differences of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results and discussion

Characterization of isolated bacteria from fermented foods

In this study, MRS agar was used as a selective media for the isolation of *Lactobacilli* from different fermented food products, which are made of fish, milk, soybean and mustard leaves. Four isolates namely DF, LS, BK and FM, each from the four different fermented foods were selected for further study. Preliminary characterization of the four isolates showed that all were gram positive bacteria and only one among them exhibited catalase activity (Table 1).

Table 1. Preliminary characterization of bacterial isolates from fermented foods

Source	Isolates	Catalase activity	Shape	Gram stain
Fermented fish	DF	Negative	Rod	Gram positive
Fermented milk	LS	Negative	Coccus	Gram positive
Fermented soybean	BK	Negative	Rod	Gram positive
Fermented mustard leaves	FM	Positive	Coccus	Gram positive

In order to evaluate the growth of bacterial isolates in MRS media at 37°C under normal conditions in the absence of environmental stress, colony forming cells were determined by spreading diluted samples of each isolate on MRS agar plates. Colony forming capacity (CFU ml⁻¹) of the isolates was compared and cell viability was recorded by counting the number of colonies in MRS agar.

CFU ml⁻¹ values were estimated from serial diluted bacterial cultures upto 10⁻⁶ dilutions as given in Figure 1. The result showed that CFU per ml was comparable and there was no significant difference in all the cultures tested.

Fig. 1. Estimation of bacterial growth and viability by colony forming units per ml (CFU ml⁻¹) of the four isolates at 10⁻⁶ dilution. Sample source: DF (Fermented dry fish), LS (Fermented milk), FM (Fermented mustard), BK (Fermented soybean)

To check the effect of pH on the bacterial isolates, growth was compared by incubation of cultures at different pH levels under similar culture conditions. Two isolates (FM and LS) were employed for comparison of growth at different pH conditions ranging from pH 1.5 to 6.5 in MRS media. Optimal growth was observed when the bacterial cultures were incubated overnight in pH 6.5, however, growth declined as the pH was lowered (Figure 2). There is a decline in growth with decrease in pH, where no growth was observed at highly acidic pH 1.5, however, the viability test as indicated by bacterial capacity to form colonies suggests that some bacteria still survived at pH 2.5 as shown in Table 2.

Lactic acid bacteria (LAB) are known fermentative microorganisms that may alter pH levels when organic acids are present. Most of these lactic acid bacteria grow preferably at pH 6 - 7. LAB, which creates lactic acid and metabolites like antioxidants, organic acids, and antibacterial compounds, modifies and enhances intestinal microbial homeostasis (Rao et al., 2004). The importance of understanding the physiology of lactic acid bacteria towards stress was also emphasized to create probiotics with enhanced functionality (Rault et al., 2009).

Subsequently, in order to determine the effect of nutrient limitation stress on the bacterial growth, we have chosen isolate BK and growth was estimated in the absence of certain essential nutrients and carbon sources. The growth of BK was estimated by measuring the OD_{600nm} after 18 hr incubation in MRS media in the absence of magnesium sulphate, glucose or sodium acetate respectively (Figure 3). Simultaneously, a non-aerated culture with limited oxygen supply was also employed to determine the aerobic or anaerobic behaviour of the bacterial isolate.

Fig. 2. Growth of isolates (a) FM and (b) LS at different pH conditions in MRS media at 37°C. (A $p \leq 0.5$ was considered statistically significant and average deviation < 10%)

Table 2. Colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) of isolate FM at different pH levels (*values represent average of 3 replicates with deviation < 10%)

pH	Dilution factor	Number of colonies*	CFU ml ⁻¹
6.5	10 ⁻⁶	409	8.1 × 10 ⁸
4.5	10 ⁻⁶	168	3.3 × 10 ⁸
3.5	10 ⁻⁶	30	0.6 × 10 ⁸
2.5	10 ⁻⁶	10	0.2 × 10 ⁸
1.5	10 ⁻⁶	-	-

The decline in growth was observed in the absence of magnesium, sodium acetate and glucose. However, there was a marginal difference when either magnesium or sodium acetate was limited. Magnesium sulphate is the source of magnesium ion which is essential for biological processes such as bacterial replication, cell wall synthesis and serves as cofactors for many enzymatic reactions. Sodium acetate being a weak acid helps in maintaining the optimal pH condition crucial for the growth of lactic acid bacteria and prevents the growth of other bacteria and fungi. Bacterial growth decreased significantly but growth was still observed even in the absence of glucose after 18 hr (Figure 3 and Table 3) suggesting that bacteria may obtain carbon from sources other than glucose. However, there was a drastic decline in the growth after 24 hr possibly due to the exhaustion of all carbon sources in the media (data not shown). Although a decline in growth was observed in non-aerated culture conditions as compared with the normal aeration, growth was still observed probably due to the facultative behaviour of the bacterial isolates. This variation in growth suggests that higher level of energy produced in aerated conditions could support more bacterial growth as compared to the less energy-efficient anaerobic route. In some *lactobacillus* species such as *L. plantarum*, the presence of stress due to nutrient starvation enhances the production of bacteriocin,

survival and stability (Parlindungan et al., 2019). But the mechanisms behind this cellular process are still unclear. *Lactobacillus* adapts to nutrient stress when glucose is depleted by changing its metabolism by channeling the energy towards biosynthesis instead of biomass production. It is speculated that LAB could possibly be used for producing valuable products under appropriate conditions. It is possible therefore, that a number of useful products could possibly be generated with LAB grown under the right culture conditions. However, more research work would be required to substantiate this claim.

Fig. 3. Growth of the isolate BK under (a) non-aerated, and (b) aerated conditions in the presence and absence of magnesium sulphate, sodium acetate and glucose after 18 hr. A ($p \leq 0.5$ was considered statistically significant)

Table 3. Estimation of CFU ml⁻¹ of isolate BK in MRS agar at 10⁻⁶ dilution incubated at 37°C for 18 hrs. (* values represent average of 3 replicates with deviation < 10%)

Nutrient (MRS)	No. of colonies for Aerobic*	CFU ml ⁻¹	No. of colonies for Anaerobic*	CFU ml ⁻¹
Control	446	8.9 X 10 ⁸	317	6.3 X 10 ⁸
No Magnesium	184	3.6 X 10 ⁸	148	2.9 X 10 ⁸
No Sodium acetate	170	3.4 X 10 ⁸	106	2.1 X 10 ⁸
No Glucose	67	1.3 X 10 ⁸	40	0.8 X 10 ⁸

In order to determine the salt-tolerant property of bacterial isolates, LS and DF were grown at different NaCl concentrations ranging from 0.5 to 11.5 % in MRS media. As shown in Figure 4, both isolates exhibited optimal growth at salt concentrations ranging from 0.5% to 2 %. The OD₆₀₀ measured after 12 hours of incubation suggests that some cells are able to withstand even upto 10 % NaCl in the culture media.

Fig. 4. Growth of the bacterial isolates (a) LS and (b) DF under varying concentrations of NaCl in MRS media after 12 hr incubation at 37°C. (p value ≤ 0.5 was considered statistically significant and average deviation < 10%)

The stress caused by the presence of salts such as NaCl may signal the bacterial cells to produce more energy for survival, which was observed in another study when the level of enzymes involved in glycolysis was altered (Wang et al., 2016). Salt stress adaptation in fermented foods is important for survival and growth in their natural ecosystems and for their industrial applications. It has been shown earlier how bacteria successfully adapted to environmental stress conditions such as acid stress, bile stress and cold stress (Van de Guchte et al., 2002; Kimoto-Nira et al., 2009; Zhang et al., 2012).

Previous studies have reported the formation of biofilms by several *Lactobacilli* including *L. plantarum*, *L. rhamnosus*, *L. fermentum* and *L. reuteri* (Terraf et al., 2012; Salas-Jara et al., 2016). The

formation of biofilm by probiotics could be advantageous for promoting bacterial colonization and survival in the host's mucosa. The biofilm-forming capacity of isolates under low temperature conditions was conducted by incubation of bacterial cultures in the refrigerator at 6-7°C for 7 days. The formation of biofilm was also determined with the bacterial cultures grown at 37°C (Figure 5). Besides, this could also prevent the growth and dominance of certain pathogens (Shukla et al., 2020). It has also been reported that *L. plantarum* strains produce molecules inhibitory to pathogens when forming a biofilm (Aoudia et al., 2016).

Fig. 5. Crystal violet-based microtitre plate assay for estimation of bacterial biofilm formation in different isolates at 37°C and 6°C.

Conclusion

Gram-positive bacteria selected from different fermented food products made of fish, milk, soybean and mustard leaves were employed in this study. Stress tolerance of bacterial isolates was determined by growth (OD_{600 nm}) and colony forming units (CFU ml⁻¹) estimation at acidic pH, high salt concentration, limited nutrients, and non-aerated culture conditions. Our results showed that bacterial viability was still observed at high acidic conditions (pH 2.5) in isolates FM and LS, and also at high salt concentration (10 % NaCl) in the case of isolates LS and DF. One of the isolates (BK) exhibited viable colonies even after several hours in the absence of glucose and limited oxygen (non-aerated) conditions, possibly due to its facultative anaerobic traits. Besides, biofilm formation was also observed in all the isolates tested at different temperatures, which could be an advantage for these bacteria in thriving against pathogens and other competing microorganisms. Moreover, more extensive and in-depth analysis would be required for further assessment of bacterial stress tolerance for its implications in food safety, food quality, potential risks, and inter-species interactions in the ecological niche of fermented foods.

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Author Contributions

TTC, TRO, BK, PCZ, Z and STV conceived the concept, wrote and approved the manuscript.

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